

A CRITICAL REVIEW OF CHURNA KALPANA: BRIDGING CLASSICAL AYURVEDIC PRINCIPLES WITH THE AFI STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

Churna is a fine powder of drug or drugs. Sushka kalka, Sushka piṣṭi, Raja and Kṣhoda are the synonymous words used for churna in classics. Though 'Chūrna Kalpanā' is a prominent preparation in pharmaceutical world of Ayurveda, it is considered as an Upakalpana of kalka kalpana.^[1] The Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI) is an official government publication that serves as a legal and technical guide for the preparation of compound Ayurvedic medicines. The AFI was established to provide standardized formulas from various ayurvedic classical text books like Sarangadhara Samhita, Rasa Tarangini etc., ensuring consistency across different manufacturers. It acts as the official companion to the Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940, which mandates that any classical Ayurvedic medicine must follow the formulas prescribed in the "First Schedule," where AFI and its parts were included. Churna Kalpana holds a primary position due to its versatility, ease of administration,

and rapid absorption. The Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI) serves as the legal and technical benchmark for ensuring the safety, efficacy, and reproducibility of these polyherbal formulations.

KEYWORDS: Churna Kalpana, AFI (The Ayurvedic formulary of India), Standardization.

INTRODUCTION

The fine powder obtained after thoroughly pounding and sieving the completely dry drugs (i.e., Particular part of the drug which are mentioned in classical texts and dried thoroughly under hot sun) is called churṇa. Pounding is done either manually in khalva or Ulukhala yantra; or mechanically in pounding/pulverizing machines. Sieving is also done either manually using a clean cloth/a selected sieve; or mechanically through sieve shakers.

Churna types

❖ Depending on the particle size

1. Sthula churna- Coarse powder (Sieve size-10/44)
2. Sukshma churna- Fine powder (Sieve size-85)
3. Atyanta Sukshma churna- Very fine powder (Sieve size-120)

❖ Simple and Compound powders^[2]

1.Ekaushada churna(Simple powder):-Ex:-Haritaki churna, Trivrit Churna, Vacha Churna etc.

2.Misra churna (Compound powders):- Ex:-Sitopaladi churna, Talisadi churna, Hinguvastaka churna etc.

Churṇa- dosage, adjuvant

One karṣa (12gms) is the general dosage of 'churṇa kalpana'. These preparations are administered along with 'honey', 'water', 'milk or any other 'liquid preparation like swarasa (i.e., Ardraka sawarasa etc.,)

Shelf life

The Saviryata avadhi (shelf life) of 'Churṇa kalpana' is of 'two months' as per classical references.^[6]

As per D&C Rules 1945 - **Two years.**

Churna-prakshepaka dravya and their ratio

In relation with the general dosage of churna (one karsha; 12 gms), the ratio of 'prakshepaka dravya' will be as given below.

Table 1:

Prakshepaka dravya	Ratio with that of churna dosage
Guda (jaggery) Sita (sugar)	Equal Double
Ghr̥ta-bharjita (ghee-fried) hingu	Quantity that doesn't cause nausea
When licked with ghr̥ta, madhu, taila etc	Double
When drank with any other liquid (toya, kshira, madya, gomutra etc)	Four times

Churṇa- therapeutic usages^[3]

1. Churna on its own is used as single medicine for treatment of various number of diseases.

Ex:- Sitopaladi Churna, Talisadi Churna, Hingvashtaka Churna etc.,

2. It is used as an adjuvant along with many other medicines.

Ex: Swarna bhasma is administered along with "Trikaṭu Churna"; Abhraka bhasma is administered along with 'Talisadi Churna'.

3. It is used for preparing secondary preparations. Ex: In 'Avaleha kalpanā', 'Vaṭī kalpana' and 'Sandhāna kalpana', it is added as 'Prakṣepa dravya'. In 'Sneha kalpana' it is added as Kalka Dravya.

4. It is used for Udvartana in many skin diseases; Ex: Triphala Churna Udvartana in cases of 'Vicharcika'.

Importance of Churna Kalpana among Panchavidha Kashaya Kalpana

- **Extended Stability:-**Unlike Swarasa or Kwatha (having shorter shelf life), Whereas Churna has a superior shelf life, facilitating long-term prescriptions and easy transport for patients.
- **Dose Precision:-**The uniform nature of churna allows for exact measurement (typically 3–6g) tailored to a patient's Agni and Koshta, ensuring more consistent results than variable preparations like Kalka.
- **Adjuvant Versatility (Anupana):-**It is easily combined with vehicles like honey, ghee, or milk. This not only improves palatability but also directs the medicine to specific Dhatus (e.g., Honey for Lekhana, Ghee for Snehana).
- **Enhanced Absorption:-**The fine particle size increases surface area, promoting faster disintegration and enzymatic action compared to denser forms like Vati.
- **Diverse Routes:-**Beyond oral use (Abhyantara), its form is essential for specialized procedures like Pradhamana Nasya (nasal), Udvartana (massage), and Avachurnana (dusting).

THE AYURVEDIC FORMULARY OF INDIA^[4]

AFI was the first attempt of Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia Committee to compile the scattered information about Ayurvedic formulations to develop Pharmacopoeial standards and to meet the requirements of Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940. Drugs are mentioned as Single formulations and Compound formulations. Formulation is defined as use of one or more than one drug in the medicinal preparation.

A. Single drugs of Plant, Animal and Mineral origin have been listed.

B. Compound formulations are divided into Kastaushadis (Predominantly Plant drugs) and Rasaushadhis (Metals and Minerals). Kastaushadhi formulations such as Asavarista, Avaleha, Ghrita, Churna, Taila etc., and Rasausadhis such as Bhasma, Pisti, Lauha, Mandura, Kupipakva rasayana etc., are explained.

AFI was published in 3 parts and it contains several formulations described as per classics and mentioned the formulations as Disease wise and Type of formulation for easy accessibility along with Samanya paribhasa, Kalpana paribhasa, Puta paribhasa, Yantra paribhasa, Sodhana procedures.

Table 2:

AFI PART	YEAR	NUMBER OF FORMULATIONS	CHURNA FORMULATIONS
1.	1978 - 1 st edition 2003 - 2 nd edition	444	40
2.	2000	191	19
3.	2011	350	69

General structure of AFI formulations

- Title -Textual Reference along with Adhikarana
- Ingredients
- Method of preparation
- Dose
- Anupana
- Therapeutic uses
- Storage

General Method of preparation^[5]

Drugs mentioned in the Yoga are cleaned and dried properly. They are finely powdered and sieved. Where there are a number of drugs in a yoga, the drugs are separately powdered and sieved. Each one of them (powder) is weighed separately, and well mixed together. As Some of the drugs contain more fibrous matter than others, this method of powdering and weighing them separately, according to the Yoga, and then mixing them together, is preferred.

In manufacturing industry, however, all the drugs are cleaned, dried and powdered together by disintegrators. Mechanical shifters are also used. Salt, sugar, camphor etc., when mentioned are separately powdered and mixed with the rest at the end. Asafoetida (hingu) and salt may also be roasted, powdered and then added. Drugs like Satavari, Guduchi etc., which are to be taken fresh, is made into a paste, dried, and then added.

Characteristics and preservation

The powder is fine of at least 80 mesh sieve. It should not adhere together or become moist. The finer the powder, the better its therapeutic value. They retain potency and should be kept in air tight containers.

Table 3:^[6]

CHURNAS MENTIONED IN AFI Part- I

S.NO	FORMULATION	REFERENCE	INDICATIONS
1.	Ajamodadi Churna	Sarangadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6 (113-115)	Sula, Gridhrasi, Amavata, Sotha, Sandhi pida, Katiruja, Pristha ruja, Guda ruja, Jangha ruja, Tuni, Pratuni, Visvachi, Kaphavataroga.
2.	Avipattikara Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Amlapittādhikara 25-29	Agnimandya, Malabandha, Amlapitta, Arsa, Mutrabandha, Prameha.
3.	Amalakyadi Churna	Sarangadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(7)	Aruchi, Agnimandya, Jvara, Ajirṇa.
4.	Intuppukana Churna	Sahasrayoga, Churnaaprakarana (23)	Agnimandya
5.	Eladi Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Chardirogadhikara (21)	Kasa, Svasa.
6.	Karpuradi Churna	Sahasrayoga, Churna	Aruchi, Kasa, Svasa,

		Prakarana	ksaya.
7.	Yavanyadi Churna	Astangahridaya, (Kapitthasamaka Churna) Cikitsasthana, Adhyaya 9 (109-110 ^{1/2})	Swasa, Atisara, Grahani, kshaya, Gulma, Udara, Kasa, Agnimandya, Arsa, Pinasa, Aruci.
8.	Gomutraharithaki	Astangahridaya Uttarasthsana, Adhyaya 22	Mukha roga.
9.	Chandanadi Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Sukramehadhikara (22-23)	Kasa, Swasa, Jirṇa jvara, Prameha, Arsa, kamala.
10.	Chaturjata Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(14 ^{1/2})	Arochaka, Kaphaja roga, Visha, Vaivarnya.
11.	Citrakadi Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(108-110)	Arochaka, Amajasula, Grahani, Gulma; Agnimandya, Kaphadosha.
12.	Jatiphaladya Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(70-72 ^{1/2})	Aruchi, Atisara, Grahani, Pravahika, kasa, Svasa, Vatasleshma pratisyaya.
13.	Talisadya Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6 (130-131 ^{1/2})	Chardi, Adhmana, Kasa, Swasa, Jvara, Aruci, Ajirṇa, Atisara, Sosha, Pleeha, Grahani, Pandu.
14.	Trikatu Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Paribhashaprakarana (16)	Arochaka, Agnimandya, Ama dosa, Gala roga, Pinasa, Kustha, Swasa, Kasa, Tvakroga, Gulma, Meha, Sthaulya, Slipada.
15.	Triphala Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Haritakyadi varaga(41)	Anaha, Prameha, Netra roga, Kaphapittaroga, Kustha, Mandagni, Aruchi, Vishama jvara.
16.	Drakshadi Churna	Vaidyayogratnavali	Agnimandya, Chardi, Kshayaja Kasa, Raktapradara, Svetapradara.
17.	Navayasa Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Panduroagadhikara(22)	Pandu, Kamala, Prameha Pidaka, Hrdroga, Kustha, Arsa.
18.	Narasimha Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Vajikaranadhikara (30-33)	Kasa, Kshaya, Sukra kshaya, Jara, Ruja, Vali, Palita, Khalitya, Meha, Pandu, Adhyavata, Pinasa, Kustha, Udara, Bhagandara Mutrakrichhra, Gridhrasi, Halimaka, Vatavikara, Pittavikara, Arsa, Sleshmavikara.
19.	Narayana Churna	Astangahridaya,	Udara roga, Gulma,

		Chikitsasthana Adhyaya 15(14-16)	Anaha, Vata roga, Vitsanga, Arsa, Parikarta, Ajirṇa, Bhagandara, Paṇḍu, Kasa, Svasa, Galagraha, Hridroga, Grahani, Kustha, Mandagni, Jvara, Damṣṭra visha, Mula visha, Kritrima visha, Gara visha.
20.	Nimbadi Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Vataraktadhikara (31-33)	Udara, Amavata, Vatarakta, Kusta, Svitra, Audumbara kustha, Kotha, Charmadala, Sidhma, Pama, Vipluta Yoniroga, Kandu, Vicharcika, Dadru, kiṭibha, Sotha, Pleecha, Gulma, Pandu, Kamala, Vrana.
21.	Nyagrodhadi Churna	Yogaratanakara, Prameha Chikitsa (567)	Mutraghāta, Mutrakrichhra, Prameha, Prameha Pidaka.
22.	Panchasama Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(93-93 ^{1/2})	Adhmana, Sula, Amavata, Arsa, Udara roga.
23.	Pushyanuga Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Strirogadhikara(46-48)	Asrigdara, Sveta Pradara, Rajodosha, Arsa, Yonidosha.
24.	Balacaturbhadrika Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Balarogadhikara(40)	Atisara, Chardi, Kasa, Swasa, Jvara, Bala Sosha.
25.	Brihat Gangadhara Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(49-50)	Pravahika, Atisara, Grahani.
26.	Bhallatka Rasayana	Rasa Tarangini, Taranga 24(484-484 ^{1/2})	Udara roga, Daurbalya, Rakta kshaya.
27.	Bhaskaralavana Churna (Lavanabhaskarachurna)	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(138-141)	Agnimandya, Sula, Grahani, Vata Kaphaja Gulma, Pliha, Udara, Arsa, Kshaya, Kustha, Vibandha, Bhagandara, Sopha, Sula, Svasa, Kasa, Amavata, Hrduja; Ajirṇa.
28.	Yavani Sandava (Yavanyadi Churna)	Astangahr̥idaya Cikitsasthana, Adhyaya 5(55-56 ^{1/2})	Arochaka, Grahani, Parsva sula, Vibandha, Kasa, Pliha, Arsa.
29.	Rajanyadi Churna	Astangahr̥idaya Uttarasthana, Adhyaya 2(38)	Atisara, Grahani, Kmala, Paṇḍu, Jvara, Agnimandya, Anaha, Svasa, Kasa, Bala roga,

			Daurhalya, Vaivarnya.
30.	Vaisvanara Churna	Cakradatta, Amavata chikitsa (15-16)	Adhmana, Gulma, Parinamasula, Amavata, Hridroga, Vastiroga, Pliharoga, Sula, Anaha, Gudaroga, Vibandha, Udara, Hastapada roga.
31.	Sringyadi Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6(42 ^{1/2})	Kasa, Jvara, Swasa, Kapharoga.
32.	Samangadi Churna	Cakradatta, Arsa chikitsa(115)	Raktarsa.
33.	Samudradya Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Sula rogadohikara 77-78 ^{1/2})	Nabhi sula, Gulma, Purinama sula, Ajirṇa, Pliha, Yakrit, Vidradhi, Asthila; Kaphajasula, Vataja sula.
34.	Sitopaladi Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 6 (134-135 ^{1/2})	Arochaka, Agnimandya, Pittaja Svasa, Jvara, Kasa, Hasta pada daha, Parsva sula, Kshaya, Suptajihvatva, Urdhvagata Raktapitta.
35.	Sudarshana Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Jwaradhikara (308-312 ^{1/2})	Yakrit, Pliha vṛiddhi, Jvara, Vishama jvara, Jirna jvara, Gulma.
36.	Svalpa Nayika Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Grahanirogadohikara (82-82 ^{1/2})	Agnimandya, Grahani.
37.	Hinguvastaka Churna	Bhaisajyaratnavali, Agnimandyarogadhikara (37)	Agnimandya, Sula, Gulma, Vataroga.
38.	Hinguvadi Churna	Yogaratnakara Gulmachikitsa (522)	Adhmana, Sula, Grahani, Gulma, Hridroga, Vankshana sula, Kukshisula, Katisula.
39.	Hinguvachadi Churna (Hinguvadi Churna)	Astangahṛidaya, Cikitsasthana, Adhyaya 14(31-32)	Adhmana, Sula, Gulma, Pandu, Parsvasula, Vasttisula, Trikasula, Yonisula, Gudasula, Vibandha, Mutrasanga, Kanthabandha, Hritgraha, Aruchi, Pliharoga, Hikka, Svasa, Kasa, Agnimandya.
40.	Hutabhugadi Churna	Sahasrayoga, Churnaprakarana(22)	Agnimandya, Pandu, Sopha, Arsa.

Table 4:⁷

CHURNAS MENTIONED IN AFI Part- II

S.NO	FORMULATION	REFERENCE	INDICATIONS
1.	Agnimukha Churna	Yogaratanakara, Ajirna chikitsa,	Udavarta, Ajirna, Pliharoga, Kshaya, Udararoga, Arsa, sula, gulma, kasa, swasa.
2.	Asvagandhadi Churna	Yogaratanakara, Rajayakshma chikitsa	Vataksaya, Pittasotha, slesmakshaya, Sirobhrama, Paittikaroga, Medoroga, Kshataksiṇa, Daurbalya
3.	Astangalavana Churna	Bhaishajyaratanaivali Madatyayadhikara 15-16	Agnimandya, Madatyaya, Strotorodha.
4.	Katphaladi Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6(38-39)	Jvara, Kasa, Svasa. Aruchi, Chardi, Vayusula.
5.	Gandhaka Rasayana	Yogaratanakara, Rasayanadhikara	Viryakshaya, Agnimandya, Kandu, Kustha, Vishavikara, Atisara, Grahani, Sula, Jirnajvara, Meha, Mukharoga, Danta Roga.
6.	Dasanasamskara Churna	Bhaishajyaratanaivali Mukharogadhikara 73-74	Mukharoga, Dantaroga.
7.	Dadimastaka Churna	Bhaishajyaratanaivali Grahanirogadhikara 36-37	Grahani
8.	Naracha Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6(95-96)	Adhmana, Udararoga, Kaphapittaja sula, Gadhavitakata.
9.	Nasika Churna	Sahasrayoga, Churnaprakarana 64	Dustapinasa, Sirahkampa, Suryavartha, Siroruja, Mukhadaurgandhya, Nasika daurgandhya, Urdhvajatrugata Roga.
10.	Panchakola Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6(13-14)	Arucihi, Anaha, Pleehavridhi, Gulma, Sula, Sleshmodara.
11.	Panchanimba Churna	Bhaishajyaratanaivali Kustadhikara	Ksudra Kustha, Mahakustha
12.	Palashabijadi Churna	Rasoddhara tantra, krimi roga	Krmiroga.
13.	Musali Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6(158)	Sukra Ksaya; Dhvaja Bhanga.
14.	Laghugangadhara Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6(47-48)	Atisara; Pravahika.
15.	Laghulai Churna	Yogaratanakara, Atisarachikitsa	Sula, Anaha, Atisara.
16.	Lavangadi churna	Bhaishajyaratanaivali	Grahani, Atisara, Jvara,

		Strirogadhikara 306-310	Amatisara, Raktatisara, Sula; Sotha: Krmiroga.
17.	Vidangadi Churna	Cakradatta Krimichikitsa	Krmiroga.
18.	Sama Sarakara Churna	Bhaishajyaratanaivali Arsarogadhikara 88	Agnimandya, Kasa, Aruchi, Svasa, Kustharoga, Hrdroga.
19.	Sarasvata Churna	Bhavaprakasha Unmadadhikara adhyaya 22	Apasmaraa Unmada.

Table 5:^[8]**CHURNAS MENTIONED IN AFI Part- III**

S.NO	FORMULATION	REFERENCE	INDICATIONS
1.	Amritadi Churna	Astangahridaya, Uttarasthan, Adhyaya 39 - 160	Daha, Pittavikara, Jara, Jarajanya vyadhi, Greeshna ritu vikara.
2.	Amritoja Churna	National Institute of Ayurveda Pharmacy, Jaipur, Anubhutayoga	Chardi-Atisra janya rasakshaya, Mutrakara, Vibandha
3.	Alambushadi Churna	Brhannighantu-ratnakara, Amavata-karmavipaka	Amavata, Sothayukta vatarakta, Udararoga.
4.	Asvagandhadi Churna	Yogaratanakara, Rājajakṣmā- cikitsā 1-6	Balya, Agnimandya, Udararoga.
5.	Abhadya Churna	Bhaishajyaratnāvali, Amavāta- cikitsā-prakarana 61	Asthigatavata, Sandhigata vata, Snayugata vata, Snayugata vata, Majjagatavata, Katigraha, Gridhrasi, Manyastambha, Hanugraha, Kostagata sarvavyadhi.
6.	Amavatari Yoga	Rasacintāmaṇi, Adhyāya 9	Amavata, Samasta vatajanya vyadhi, Sandhisopha.
7.	Amari Churna	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Pravahika, Paittika pravahika, Atisara.
8.	Utpaladya Churna	Cakradatta, Jvarātisāra- cikitsā-prakarana	Pravahika, Jwaratisara.
9.	Kamalakshadi Churna	Siddhayogasangraha Rasāyanavājikarāṇādhikāra)	Kamasaktihrasa, Dourbalya, Sukrakshaya
10.	Karaviradi Yoga	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Kasa, Swasa.
11.	Karchuradi Churna	Brhannighantu-ratnākara, Sannipāta-sangrahani- karmavipāka)	Kaphavatajanya grahani, Balakshaya, Varnahrasa, Agnidourbalya
12.	Krishnabijadi Churna	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga 16	Vibandha, Ajirna, Amlapitta, Udarasula, Aruchi.
13.	Krishnadi Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6	Sisujwaratisara, Sisujwara, Sisukasa, Sisuvamana.
14.	Kshararaja Churna	B.H.U. Anubhutayoga	Udarasula, Asmari, Gulma, Sthoulya.

15.	Tumburvadi Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyāya 6 (107-109)	Sarvasula, Gulma, Adhmana, Udararoga.
16.	Tejohvadi manjana	B.H.U. Anubhutayoga	Dantasata, Dantapuya, Dantagata rakta srava.
17.	Trikatvadi Churna	Brhannighantu-ratnākara, Kshaya karmavipāka	Kasa, Swasa, kshaya
18.	Tryushanadi Churna	Bhaisajyaratnāvali, Atisāra-cikitsa-prakarana 33	Amatisara, Agnimandya.
19.	Dantadhavana Churna	Vaidyayogaratnavali; IMPCOPS, Churṇa prakaraṇa)	Dantapuya, Mukharoga, Mukhadourgandhya, Dantaroga.
20.	Dantapuyahara manjana	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Dantapuya, Dantasata Dantaroga.
21.	Dhatakyadi Churna	Bhaisajya Ratnavali, Anubhūta Yoga Prakarana 25-26	Pravahika, Atisara.
22.	Dhumayoga	Siddhayogasangraha, Kasasvasadhikara	Kasa, Swasa.
23.	Navaksharaka Churna	Gadanigraha, Prayogakhanda, churnadhikara 359-360	Raktavata, Aruchi, Pleehodara.
24.	Nagakesaradi Churna	Siddhayogasangraha, Atisāra Pravahikā Grahani Adhikāra	Pittatisara, Raktatisara, Pravahika, Udarasula.
25.	Nagakesarapurasthi Churna	Bhārata-bhaisajya-ratnākara, Part 4 -5127	Garbhakaraka, Vandhyatva.
26.	Narayana Churna	Bhaisajyaratnāvali, Atisāra-cikitsa-prakarana 103-106	Sotha, Raktatisara, Jwara, Trishna, Pandu, Haleemaka, Agnimandya, Prameha, Arsas.
27.	Pachana Churna	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Adhmana, Agnimandya.
28.	Patadhi Churna	Bhaisajyaratnāvali, Atisāra-cikitsa-prakarana) 47	Sleshmatisara, Atisara, Pravahika.
29.	Pashanabhedadi Churna	Carakasarmhita, Cikitssthāna, Adhyāya 26 60 - 61	Mutrasmari, Mutravarodha, Mutralpata.
30.	Pittantaka yoga	National Institute of Ayurveda Pharmacy, Jaipur, Anubhūtayoga	Amlapitta, Udarasula, Pittajavyadhi, Pandu, Gulma.
31.	Puyamehahara Churna	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Puyameha, Mutravarodha, Mutralpata, Mutradaha.
32.	Badaradya Churna	Gadanigraha, Prayogakhanda, Churṇādhikāra 356-358	Hridya, Vamana, Raktapitta, Jwara, Kasa.
33.	Brihad Agnimukha Churna	Cakradatta, Agnimandya-cikitsa-prakarana 30-38	Mandagni, Ajirna, Gulma, Pleeharoga, Udararoga, Antravridhi, Asthila, Vatarakta.
34.	Bhunimbadi	Gadanigraha,	Yakrid vidradi, Pleeharoga,

	Churna	Prayogakhanda, Cūrṇādhikāra 398-399	Arsas, Mandagni, Grahani.
35.	Madhumehari Churna	National Institute of Ayurveda Pharmacy, Jaipur, Anubhūtayoga	Prameha, Madhumeha, Ikshumeha, Laalameha.
36.	Madhyamanikya Churna	Bhaiṣajyaratnavali, Grahaniroga-cikitsā-prkaraṇa 87-89	Agnimandya, Vatatisara, Pittatisara, Kaphatisara, Swasa Kasa, Jwara, Sula, Rajyakshma, Pleehavridhi, Amavata, Arsas, Kusta, Vatarakta, Kantaroga.
37.	Marichadi Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5112	Udararoga, Pleeharoga, Mandagni, Gulma, Arsas.
38.	Mahakhandava Churna	Sarṅgadharaśamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6 – 77-82	Mandagni, Ajirna, Kasa, Atisara, Kantaroga, Jatararoga, Mukharoga, Visuchika, Adhmana, Arsas, Gulma, Krimi, Chardi, Svasa.
39.	Mahatalisadi Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5121	Peenasa, Rajyakshma, Vatapaittika Hridroga, Mutrakriccha, Netraroga, Pnadu, All types of Vatarogas, pittarogas, kapharogas, Galagraha, Sula, Arsas, Bhagandhara, Swarabhanga.
40.	Mahanimbadi Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5552	Kustaroga, Vidradhi, Raktavikara, Vibandha.
41.	Mahasarasvati Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5124	Buddhijadya, Vakdosha, Mandabuddhi.
42.	Mashadi Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5136	Somaroga, Napumsakatha, Balakshaya.
43.	Mundyadi Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5140	Antravridhi, Balya, Rasayana, Vrishya, Daha.
44.	Mutrakara Churna	National Institute of Ayurveda Pharmacy, Jaipur, Anubhitayoga	Mutraghata, Mutrasmari.
45.	Methikadi Churna	Gadanigraha, Prayogakhanda, Cūrṇādhikāra - 373-376	Raktavata, Pittajanya Upadrava, Sannipataja roga, Mudagarbha nasaka.
46.	Yavaksharadi yoga	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5752	Agnimandya, Amavata, Sthoulya, Nanadeshaja jaladoshaja vyadhi.
47.	Yavaksharadya Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5753	Sula and Upadrava yukta gulma, Agnimandya.
48.	Yastyadi Churna	Bharata-bhaiṣajya-ratnākara, Part 4 - 5769	Sthanavrana, Kasa, Vrana, Vicharchika, Pama, Udarda
49.	Rasanjanadi	Bhaiṣajyaratnavali, Atisara-	Pravridha Raktatisara,

	Churna	cikitsa-prkaraṇa 101-102	Pravahika, Raktarsas.
50.	Lavangadi Churna	Bhaiṣajyaratnavali, Rajayakshma-cikitsa- prkaraṇa 23-25	Agnimandya, Dourbalya, Napumsakata, Urovibandha, Vibandha, Tamaka swasa, Galagraha, Kasa, Hikka, Yakshma, Pinasa, Sangrahani, Atisara, Arbuda, Bagandhara, Prameha, Gulma.
51.	Lavanatritiyadya Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6 – 99-106	Yakritroga, Pleeharoga, Katisula, Gudaroga, Hridroga, Kukshisula, Arsas, Vistambha, Mandagni, Gulma, Pleehodara, Hikka, Adhmana, Swasa, Kasa.
52.	Vadavanala Churna	Sarngadharasamhita, Madhyamakhandā, Adhyaya 6 – 114	Mandagni, Ajirna, Aruchi.
53.	Vidaryadi Churna	Siddhayogasangraha, Rasayana Vajikaranadhikara	Veeryakshaya, Veeryahrasa, Seeghrapathana, Kamasakthihrasa.
54.	Visaladi Churna	Chakradatta Panduroga chikitsa prakaraṇa 19-20	Pandu, Jwara, Daha, Swasa. Kasa, Swasa, Aruchi, Gulma, Anaha, Vatavyadhi, Raktapitta.
55.	Vyoshadika Churna	Bhaiṣajyaratnavali, Nasaroga cikitsa prakaraṇa 4-5	Pinasa, Kasa, Swasa, Aruchi, Swarabheda
56.	Satapatriyadi Churna	Siddhayogasangraha, Agnimandya Ajirnadhikara	Vidagdhajirna, Amlapitta, Pachanavikarajanya mukhapaka.
57.	Suntiyadi Churna - 1	Bhaiṣajyaratnavali, Nasaroga cikitsa prakaraṇa 35	Amatisara, Pravahika, Grahani.
58.	Suntiyadi Churna - 2	Brhannighaṇṭu-ratnakara, Aruchi-karmavipaka	Kasa, Swasa, Lalasrava, Hridroga, Aruchi, Galamaya, mukhapaka.
59.	Sodashanga Churna	Yogachintamani, Adhyaya 2 1 - 2	Jwarasula, Kasa, Swasa, Agnimandya.
60.	Samasarkara Churna	Cakradatta, Kasa-Cikitsa- Prakaraṇa	Kasa, Jwara, Arochaka, Prameha, Gulma, Swasa, Agnimandya, Grahnidoshā.
61.	Sameeragajakesari	Bharata Bhaiṣajya Ratnakara, Part-5, Rasa Prakaraṇa 8153	Kubjavata, Khanjavata, Gridhrasi, Sopha, Kamapavata, Prathanaka, Visuchika, Apasmara.
62.	Sarpagandha misrana	CGHS Formulary, Anubhutayoga	Hridroga, Anidra, Chittodvega.
63.	Samudradya churna (Dvithiya)	Gadanigraha, Prayogakhanda, Curnadhikara 254 - 255	Vatajirna, Grahabadha, Gulmavata, Prameha, Vishamavata, Kamala,

			Pandu, Visuchika, Swasa, Kasa.
64.	Saraswatha churna	Vaidyayogaratnavali, IMPCOPS, Curṇaprakarana	Apasmara, Masthishkagata vikara, Udara.
65.	Sougandhika churna	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Raktavikara, Vibandha.
66.	Snuhimaricha yoga	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Vibandha, Arsas.
67.	Swarnapatryadi churna	B.H.U. Anubhūtayoga	Vibandha, mukhapaka, Amlapitta.
68.	Svadishta virechana churna	Bhaiṣajyasarasangraha, churṇa prakarana	Kostabaddhatha, Arsas.
69.	Haridradi churna	Bhaiṣajyaratnavali, Hikkaswasa cikitsa prakaraṇa 16	Swasaroga, Anurjatajanita vyadhi.

DISCUSSION

Churna Kalpana remains a fundamental pillar of Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals due to its therapeutic versatility, rapid absorption, and ease of administration. While traditionally classified as an Upakalpana (secondary preparation) of Kalka, its importance is elevated by its role as a base for various secondary formulations like Vati and Asava etc.,. One of the major advantages of Churna is that it is naturally devoid of synthetic preservatives. **The drying, roasting and pulverizing processes reduces moisture content, which helps to inhibit microbial growth and enhances shelf life without the need for chemical additives.** This makes Churna formulations safer, more natural, and aligned with traditional Ayurvedic principles of purity (Shuddhata) and minimal processing. The standardization provided by the Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI) across its three parts has been instrumental in transitioning these classical powders into the modern regulatory framework. By defining precise particle sizes, dosage metrics, and shelf-life standards (extending from the classical 2 months to the statutory 2 years), the AFI ensures the safety, reproducibility, and global efficacy of both simple (Ekaushada) and compound (Misra) Churnas in contemporary clinical practice.

CONCLUSION

Churna Kalpana is a fundamental Ayurvedic dosage form where dried herbs are powdered and sieved. The Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI) provides the modern "gold standard" for making these traditional formulas consistent and safe. AFI-guided Churna preparations ensure precise ingredient ratios, sieving methods, and shelf-life protocols, enhancing reproducibility and safety for clinical use. They bridge traditional wisdom from texts like

Sarangadhara Samhita etc. with contemporary quality controls, such as particle size analysis and microbial testing.

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